

Methodical system of formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers

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Annotation. The issues of forming the information and communication competence of foreign language teachers are considered. A methodological system of the process of forming this competence has been developed. The main components of the methodological system for the formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers are highlighted.

Key words: Information and communication technologies; competence of a foreign language teacher; advanced training of foreign language teachers; Methodical system.

Following , we understand the methodological system as a set of the main components of the educational process that determine the selection of material for classes, the forms of its presentation, methods and means of teaching, as well as ways of organizing it. From the standpoint of a systematic approach, the methodological system of education is a single holistic complex that allows you to model the process of education and upbringing. The main components of the methodological system are the goals, content of training, principles, methods, means, skills developed during training, as well as the results of the transformation of the educational process with an assessment of the quality of solving the problem. All components of the methodological system are in a certain hierarchical relationship.

The structure of the methodological system for the formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers includes:

- prerequisites that actualize the need for the formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers;
- the target block, which is formed under the influence of the environment and influences the choice of an approach to learning, principles, content, forms, methods, teaching aids arising from the chosen approach that implements the goals of learning;
- a theoretical block, including methodological approaches and general didactic principles for the formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers;
- a technological block consisting of the content of education, forms of education, pedagogical conditions, teaching aids, methods that contribute to the successful formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers;

- evaluative and effective block for evaluating the results of the formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers, including criteria, indicators and levels of its formation.

The main goal of the proposed methodological system is the formation of information and communication competence of foreign language teachers. In our work, the development of a methodological system for the formation of information and communication competence of a foreign language teacher will be based on the provisions of the competence-based, personality-oriented, personality-activity and system approaches, as well as the concept of informatization of education.

In terms of content, the accepted methodological approaches perform a heuristic function in the knowledge of the chosen object of reality and are thus a tool for searching for new knowledge.

Particular attention should be paid to the concept of informatization of education. Within the framework of the Integrated Program of the Russian Academy of Education "Information and Communication Technologies in General, Vocational and Additional Education", the main directions of informatization of education in the domestic school were identified, including a wide range of aspects of informatization (from the development of methodology to the improvement of the processes of informatization of the management of educational institutions), as well as theoretical fundamentals and scientific and methodological support of the new scientific direction of pedagogical science "Theory and methods of informatization of education".

The formation of linguistic competence occurs throughout all the years of learning a foreign language and is a multi-component and multi-level process, consisting of several stages, which can be correlated with the corresponding level of education in a general educational institution of a school type. The formation of the main level of linguistic competence correlates with the second stage of education at school (5 - 7 (8) grades), occupying an intermediate position between the initial (1-4 grades) and advanced levels (8 (9) - 11 (12) grades). To ensure the formation of linguistic competence, it is necessary to appropriately model the teaching and educational space, which involves the use of educational materials selected taking into account the principle of "methodological authenticity" and modern technologies for teaching foreign languages in the aspect of intercultural communication.

The formation of linguistic competence in students at the second stage of education of a school with in-depth study of foreign languages contributes to the development of social and psychological qualities of a person, such as: critical and reflective thinking, tolerance, empathy, which are of a non-linguistic nature. These qualities are manifested

in the ability to take into account the factor of the mentality of the people / peoples (in our case, these are the peoples of Spain), which leads to the development and implementation of the features of a secondary linguistic personality: the ability to understand a different social reality, the formation in the minds of students of a "picture of the world" characteristic of native speakers of the language being studied, the ability to compare the socio-cultural experience of the people speaking the target language with their own experience.

The formation of linguistic, speech, sociolinguistic, sociocultural, linguistic-cultural, cultural competencies, as well as the development of secondary language personality traits in schoolchildren, is possible only when a certain level of linguistic competence is reached, the formation of which is carried out throughout all the years of learning a foreign language in a specially modeled learning environment with the aim of personal development of students and is a multi-component and multi-level process, consisting of several stages. The effectiveness of intercultural communication between representatives of different linguo-societies directly depends on the formed TM foreign language communicative competencies in communicators. Linguistic competence at the second stage of education is fundamental for the formation of all other competencies, in particular, and communicative competence, in general.

List of used literature:

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